

Resource Allocation with Service Level Constraints in Point-to-Multipoint Metro-Core Networks

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Abstract: We analyze the cost-effectiveness of a point-to-multipoint metro-core (P2MP) architecture in scenarios where service-level requirements allow for dynamic allocation and sharing of spectrum. Significant cost savings are demonstrated compared to utilizing point-to-point (P2P) transceivers. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The Digital Sub-Carrier (DSC) technique employed in coherent P2MP transceivers offers exceptional flexibility in resource allocation within metro aggregation networks [1]. DSC supports the deployment of a “hub-and-spoke” architecture, which reduces the number of required transceivers by removing opto/electro/opto conversions, thus resulting in significant cost savings [1]. In the hub-and-spoke approach, the access nodes reside in horseshoes and are equipped with lower capacity P2MP transceivers (spokes). The metro-core nodes at the endpoints of the horseshoe are equipped with higher capacity transceivers (hubs) and multiple spokes communicate with the hub over the horseshoe. The baseline hub-and-spoke architecture, where the hubs and horseshoes are statically associated, was extended with the use of light-trees that enable the hub placement deeper into the metro-core network [2], as shown in Fig. 1. We demonstrated that the disassociation of hubs and horseshoes results in an even better utilization of the available DSCs at the hub, since it is possible to multiplex spokes from multiple horseshoes. In addition, placing the hubs deeper into the metro-core network reduces the need for P2P connections between the hubs and backbone nodes.

The previous works on the light-tree architecture considered a deterministic traffic scenario, where spokes are allocated with a fixed number of DSCs. In a more realistic scenario, the traffic conditions are dynamic and a static allocation would result in spokes being either under- or over-provisioned. P2MP hub transceivers support the dynamic re-allocation of the available DSCs based on the instantaneous spoke demands, partially addressing the problem. Still, it is challenging to re-assign spokes to hubs without service disruption if the hub capacity is exceeded and it is beneficial to pre-plan the assignment of spokes based on their historical traffic patterns, ensuring that the aggregated traffic remains within the hub capacity. This work assesses the capability of the light-tree based P2MP architecture to support dynamic allocation without service disruption and provide a pre-determined service level to the spokes, while remaining cost-effective. To this end, we propose a heuristic algorithm that considers the physical layer impairments of the metro-core network, as well as the desired service level, to construct the light-trees in an efficient manner. Our results show the light-tree architecture maintains its effectiveness compared to the “hub-and-spoke” even when traffic conditions are non-deterministic. It is also reported that the trade-off between service level and cost remains relatively unchanged with the physical layer, and both P2MP architectures provide similar trade-offs for several traffic scenarios.

2. Problem Statement and Allocation Algorithm

In the light-tree architecture of Fig. 1, the access nodes are equipped with coherent P2MP spoke transceivers and their hub counterparts are placed at the metro-core and backbone nodes. The spokes connect to hubs via light-trees and the spoke-to-hub assignment meets the two following criteria: first, the hub transceiver must have an adequate number of DSCs to ensure that the traffic from the spokes can be dynamically allocated with the required service level. The associated probability is expressed as P_b and planning for the maximum traffic corresponds to $P_b=0$. Second, the OSNR degradation from a spoke to its designated hub remains within pre-defined levels to

Fig. 1. P2MP architecture based on light-trees.

support the modulation format that is used in the communication [3]. Without loss of generality, since the presented methodology is applicable to any distribution, we assume that the traffic at each spoke l is an independent truncated gaussian random variable described by parameters $\{T_{min}^l, T_{ave}^l, T_{max}^l, \sigma_T\}$, which correspond to the minimum, most probable, maximum traffic value and the traffic variance, respectively (in Gb/s). The spoke traffic is converted to discrete DSCs, depending on the available transceiver technology. We consider two technologies: (a) fixed modulation format (16-QAM) transceivers, where DSCs carry 25 Gb/s each, and (b) flexible modulation format transceivers (16-QAM, 8-QAM, QPSK, BPSK), which utilize an equal bandwidth per DSC (4 GHz) but achieve a lower data rate. The number of DSCs that are required to serve the spoke traffic is then increased by a factor of a in flexible transceivers and the traffic parameters are expressed in a unified manner as $\alpha \cdot \{SC_{min}^l, SC_{ave}^l, SC_{max}^l, \sigma\}$. The DSC distribution is generated after the discretization of the truncated Gaussian and the probability $p^l(n)$ that the l -th spoke requests n DSCs is calculated from

$$p^l(n) = \frac{\text{erf}\left(\frac{\min\{n, a \cdot SC_{max}^l\} - a \cdot SC_{ave}^l}{a \cdot \sigma\sqrt{2}}\right) - \text{erf}\left(\frac{\max\{n-1, a \cdot SC_{min}^l\} - a \cdot SC_{ave}^l}{a \cdot \sigma\sqrt{2}}\right)}{\text{erf}\left(\frac{a \cdot SC_{max}^l - a \cdot SC_{ave}^l}{a \cdot \sigma\sqrt{2}}\right) - \text{erf}\left(\frac{a \cdot SC_{min}^l - a \cdot SC_{ave}^l}{a \cdot \sigma\sqrt{2}}\right)}, n = [a \cdot SC_{min}^l], \dots, [a \cdot SC_{max}^l]. \quad (1)$$

The size C^l of a spoke transceiver (in terms of number of DSCs) is determined by requesting that the spokes' DSCs exceed C^l with probability P_b or lower, following $\sum_{n > C^l} p^l(n) \leq P_b$. Regarding the hubs, the probability that exactly n DSCs are occupied ($p^h(n)$) is calculated by convoluting the distributions of the connected spokes $\{l_1, \dots, l_m\}$ as $p^h(n) = p^{l_1}(n) * \dots * p^{l_m}(n)$. The hub transceiver capacity C^h is determined in a similar fashion following $\sum_{n > C^h} p^h(n) \leq P_b$. For the OSNR degradation, we performed simulations with the GN model, assuming that 32 light-trees with 32 DSCs each co-exist. It was found that the metro OSNR can be approximated as $OSNR_m(dB) = 26.0 - 10 \log_{10}(2N_s)$, where N_s is the number of 80 km links that are traversed by the light-trees and a factor of 2 is included to approximate the impact of ROADMs. The metro and horseshoe OSNRs are used to calculate the total OSNR as $OSNR^{-1} = OSNR_m^{-1} + OSNR_h^{-1}$ and determine if the spoke can connect to a hub using a specific modulation format.

The spoke assignment problem is a variant of the bin-packing problem with P_b constraints [4], and limitations that are imposed by the modulation format selection and hub placement. The utilization of high-order modulation formats reduces the spoke transceiver sizes, since fewer DSCs are required to transport the same traffic from the spokes, and the reduced number of DSCs also allows for more spokes to be connected per hub, given the constrained hub DSC capacity. However, the reach of the spokes is limited, the hubs are placed at intermediate metro-core nodes and additional P2P connections are required to reach the backbone. Lower capacity modulation formats significantly reduce the cost of P2P at the expense of using more DSCs (more and larger size P2MP transceivers) to address the increased DSC variability, following Eq. (1). These attributes make the problem NP-hard and we propose a heuristic algorithm to solve it more efficiently, especially at larger problem sizes. In the proposed heuristic, we first sort the spoke requests SC_{ave}^l in descending order, similar to the best-fit decreasing algorithm that efficiently solves the bin-packing problem. We then consider each available modulation format starting with 16-QAM and for each modulation format our algorithm sequentially checks the ordered spokes that have not been allocated to hubs in a previous step. For each ordered spoke, the algorithm calculates its DSC distribution $p^l(n)$ for the current modulation format using Eq. (1), and the set S^l of reachable metro-core and backbone nodes. Then, the algorithm utilizes the hub placement locations S^h to identify nodes in S^l that already host hubs, and the probability distributions of the reachable hubs are convoluted with the distribution of the spoke $p^h(n) * p^l(n)$. The algorithm only keeps reachable hubs that satisfy $\sum_{n > C^h} p^h(n) * p^l(n) \leq P_b$, i.e., hubs where P_b is not exceeded; if multiple hubs satisfy this criterion, then the spoke is assigned to the hub with the highest resulting probability with a goal to fully utilize the hub capacities. After the assignment, the hub probability distribution and placement locations are updated following $p^h(n) \leftarrow p^h(n) * p^l(n)$ and $S^h \leftarrow S^h \cap S^l$, respectively. However, it is also possible that no existing hub can be reached; in this case, the algorithm examines if the spoke may further lower its modulation format to reach a backbone node. If this is not possible, then a new hub is introduced at an intermediate metro-core node: the new hub distribution is initialized to that of the spoke $p^h(n) \leftarrow p^l(n)$, and the hub locations are initialized to the set of reachable nodes $S^h \leftarrow S^l$.

3. Results and Discussion

The proposed algorithm was evaluated via simulations using realistic topologies of the TID network [5]. The flexible P2MP transceivers support {16-QAM, 8-QAM, QPSK, BPSK}, with respective required OSNRs equal to {15.1, 12.5, 8.5, 5.5} dB [3], while the fixed transceivers were limited to 16-QAM. The OSNRs at the horseshoe outputs were set equal to the 16-QAM OSNR level plus an additional budget: $OSNR_h(dB) = 15.1 + budget$, allowing for propagation impairments inside the metro-core network by expanding the budget and/or lowering the modulation format. The

Fig. 2. (a) Transceiver cost for two different service levels P_b and traffic variabilities σ , (b) relative cost reduction from increasing P_b in a traffic scenario with asymmetry towards the maximum, and (c) symmetry around the mean.

transceiver sizes were set equal to $\{32, 16, 8, 4\}$ DSCs, with respective costs of $\{3, 2, 1.5, 1\}$ arbitrary units (a.u.) for the P2MP transceivers, while 90% of the previous values were considered for equal size P2P transceivers [6].

Fig. 2(a) presents simulation results for the total transceiver cost in TID domain A for $P_b=0$ and 0.1 and traffic variances $\sigma=0.1$ and 3. The results correspond to the average of 100 simulations: in each simulation the spokes required a random number of DSCs SC_{ave}^l generated uniformly within $\{1 \dots 20\}$, while the distribution minima and maxima were $\{SC_{min}^l, SC_{max}^l\} = \{0.90, 1.40\} \cdot SC_{ave}^l$. The figure shows that the average transceiver cost increases with the service level and the traffic variance, and this is clear for both fixed and flexible P2MP transceivers. As expected, the costs for the two service levels are quite similar for the lower traffic variance when flexible transceivers are used, and practically identical for fixed transceivers. At a higher variance, however, lowering the service level provides a significant cost reduction for both fixed and flexible transceivers. Fig. 2(b) quantifies the percentage cost reduction that can be achieved by increasing $P_b=0$ to $P_b=0.1$ at a variance equal to $\sigma=3$. For the asymmetric traffic scenario of Fig. 2(a) with requests within $\{1 \dots 20\}$ DSCs, the expected gain amounts to 7% - 9% for fixed transceivers and 4% - 7% for flexible transceivers. The figure also includes simulations for a lower traffic load of $\{1 \dots 10\}$ DSCs per spoke and the results are comparable, albeit somewhat smaller (3% - 5% for fixed transceivers and 3% - 5% for flexible transceivers). The cost benefit is also relatively flat with the OSNR budget and demonstrates that both the baseline hub-and-spoke, which corresponds to fixed transceivers with zero budget, and the light-tree architectures provide a similar trade-off between cost and service level. To verify this observation under different traffic conditions, we also performed simulations for a symmetric traffic scenario where the distribution minima and maxima were $\{SC_{min}^l, SC_{max}^l\} = \{0.75, 1.25\} \cdot SC_{ave}^l$. This scenario is shown in Fig. 2(c) and the results confirm that both P2MP architectures benefit similarly from decreasing the service level.

3. Conclusion

We presented results for a planning algorithm that constructs light-trees in an efficient manner, while considering the probabilistic traffic distributions of the spokes. The algorithm ensures that the hub capacities are observed by the connected spokes with a high probability, to provide a pre-determined service level. The results show that the light-tree architecture maintains its cost benefit compared to the hub-and spoke at such dynamic traffic conditions. Both P2MP architectures also exhibit similar cost-to-service-level trade-offs.

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